

PSYCHOLOGICAL ASPECTS OF LEARNING A FOREIGN LANGUAGE

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Abstract: This scientific article examines the factors affecting the successful learning of a foreign language. The author shows their interdependence and influence on the process of learning a foreign language. The article discusses methodological and psychological aspects of learning a foreign language.

Key words: foreign language, factor, motivation, ability, obstacle, methodology, psychology, skill, technology.

INTRODUCTION

In modern conditions, the issues of learning English are becoming more and more important. This language is international, serves as a leading means of intercultural and interlinguistic communication, serves as a means of forming a global identity, and is the most studied foreign language in the world. In such conditions, it is not surprising that English is mandatory for studying at school, college, and university.

At the same time, it has been repeatedly pointed out that many people learn English, but only a few are good at it. Despite the fact that the importance of good language teaching in modern conditions is recognized by everyone, a person with a non-linguistic education who knows English well is not a very common phenomenon in our country.

At present, active methodical research is being carried out in linguodidactics for effective methods of mastering the English language. In addition, the concept of "effective way" includes the concept of "fast way", because the accelerating pace of life in the 21st century does not allow a person to study English methodically for several years, it is possible they believe in a non-existent result. in the future. Modern man needs immediate results, already on the way. On the road, the result is understood, of course, not fluency, but at least speaking in English on everyday topics in the simplest situations of social interaction. The same didactic methods and techniques can be effective in one situation and ineffective in another.

Considering all this, it seems that only a didactic understanding of the problem of learning English is not enough. It is necessary to pay more attention to the factors that affect this process, but are outside of linguodidactics. The most important of them is psychological, and in this article we will show their connection with purely methodological aspects.

Among the main psychological aspects of learning English, the following are the most important: motivation and interest in learning the language; language learning ability; the ratio of language and speech in learning; language barrier.

Motivation is the main factor in language learning. As in any activity, if a person does not want to do something or does it by force, he will not achieve a high result. The result in language learning can only bring motivation to achieve success. Motivation to avoid failure can be a one-off. For example, a student is afraid of failing an exam with a demanding English teacher. It will pass the test, maybe not badly, but such local success will have no long-term impact.

The point is that it is necessary to gradually form and develop foreign language skills, and then to maintain them throughout life, of course, this cannot be done by force. Demand in the labor market is an important motivation factor for people learning English.

Indeed, in the context of the globalization of the economy, there is an increase in trade and business relations between countries. This determines the rapid development of international firms throughout the world, including in Russia. They are actively developing their business, expanding, opening new departments and representative offices, thereby creating new jobs. Working in such firms, as a rule, is more promising for a specialist both financially and career-wise. At the same time, it imposes more requirements, among which, in addition to the basic qualifications, is the knowledge of the English language. Knowledge of the English language of employees is an important factor of the company's economic competitiveness, that is, it is a part of its intellectual capital.

In this regard, when learning the language, at first there should be an attitude that the English language itself works only as a means of receiving and transmitting this or that information. If a person is interested in the information they are working with (i.e., English language materials), they will also be interested in the process of learning English. Here, the psychological component is closely related to the most important methodological component, that is, the content of teaching English, which should be selected in accordance with the interests and age characteristics of students in order to maintain a high level of motivation.

Despite the obviousness of the above arguments, many people who start learning English well still do not follow through. Why do they lose motivation? The fact is that English, unlike, for example, mastering a computer system or learning to drive a car, requires constant and systematic practice, and most people are not ready for this. Often, some circumstances prevent it from doing so, and it becomes a convenient reason, an excuse. This requires certain voluntary actions that have not been taken into account. Another feature of English as a skill is that it seems unnecessary in everyday life. In fact, if all the information is in Russian, if you are in the environment of your native language and feel comfortable in it, it takes strong willpower to create an artificial foreign language environment for yourself. On the other hand, many people learned English without going to countries where it is the official language, and it cannot be said that they have some kind of superpowers.

Abilities are called characteristics of a person with psychological characteristics that determine the success of acquiring knowledge, skills and abilities, but they themselves are not reduced to their existence. When learning English, it is necessary to talk about linguistic knowledge and speech skills in four types of speech activity: speaking, listening, writing, reading.

Psychology denies that abilities are similar to knowledge, skills, and habits, and at the same time emphasizes their unity. Activity is necessary for the manifestation of abilities, which, in turn, cannot be carried out without abilities. In the process of learning English, it can be clear whether a person has abilities or not. English language skills, as well as other areas of human activity, are interrelated with interest and motivation. The better a person does something, the more interesting it becomes, because he learns more and more new things and feels the practical benefit of the acquired skills. In the modern world, practical benefit is one of the main factors of motivation, and motivation also grows due to the desire to achieve better and better results, a person understands that he is achieving a lot with relatively little effort.

On the other hand, if the motivation to learn English does not come primarily from the language itself, but depends on some other external factors, it can primarily develop language skills through regular and conscious practice. Often, teachers say that there are no people who do not know English in order to increase the motivation of students, because if a person speaks Russian, it means that everything is fine in the brain processes responsible for speech, so of course he can also speak English .

English proficiency is an objective advantage that must be developed through constant practice, otherwise it will level off. Constant practice is the key to success from a purely methodological point of view. In fact, all the rules of English grammar can be said in an hour. It is possible to learn a few thousand words in a very short time, if you clearly set such a task for yourself, but it is not only to learn the language material once, but also to never forget it, and this is the most difficult thing Even English majors will admit to feeling a little insecure after a month or two of not practicing, like an out-of-shape athlete. The principle "we only know what we remember" is more applicable to learning a foreign language than to any other field of human activity.

Lack of ability is often used as an excuse for not wanting to learn English. The objectively low level of complexity in the early stages of learning this language allows us to say that almost anyone can master it to one degree or another, in contrast to, for example, more complex Eastern languages.

The problem of interdependence of language and speech in connection with learning English can be formulated as follows: where to start and what to prioritize? All methods and approaches to teaching foreign languages can be divided into two large groups: from language to speech and from speech to language. However, it is wrong to say that speaking skills are not formed when learning from language to speech. It is formed passively and this process happens quite slowly. Therefore, in order to master the language in this way and learn to speak it well, you need to study it for a very long time, and the result is not immediately visible, it is permissible only in cases where a person has a unique personality. is interested in the language itself. As a rule, such people become professional linguists.

Learning from speech to language is called communicative. In it, the highest value is not the formal correctness of the spoken sentence, but not its linguistic content, but its content, the student's communicative motivation and speech act itself. With such learning, the language should not be an end in itself, but should act as a means of receiving and transmitting information. If the language is clearly taught as a means of speech, its main communicative function is much better.

Communicative education appeared in the 1970s and 1980s, when a clear pragmatic direction of scientific research was manifested both in the general conceptual position of science methodology and in the technology of teaching foreign languages. Methodical approaches have acquired a clear communicative character. A radical turn to natural communication in the process of learning this language led to the orientation of this process to the formation of communicative competence, which was then carried out taking into account the situational and personal factors that ensure the ability to communicate in the language being studied. to determine the specific features of speech behavior in a foreign language.

Strategic and discursive competencies. These components of communicative competence are closely related to issues of rhetoric. It answers questions such as how to work in an oral presentation, what is the structure of a speech, how to properly interact with the audience,

and more. It's no secret that even if we speak our native language, knowing words and their stylistic features is not difficult for us, it is far from always and not everyone is able to build a speech reliably and logically and thus achieve the intended goal. the effect of the word. This is largely due to the fact that students' oral statements in the classroom, both in a foreign language and in their native language, often express the speech only in form, not in substance. Often, communicative learning is considered simplistically as a process in which a person simply speaks English and does not practice grammar, vocabulary, etc. at all. This concept is a misinterpretation of communicative technique. It has its place to work on all aspects of language, including grammar, but this happens on the basis of real situations of speech interaction caused by certain didactic forms, methods and techniques. Here, psychology is very closely connected with didactics.

Often, communicative learning is taken as a simplistic process that does not practice grammar, vocabulary and vocabulary when it is simply done in private English. This concept is a misinterpretation of communicative technique. He does all the actions of the language, to work on this grammar, but this happens on the basis of the real benefit of the influence of creating certain didactic forms, methods and methods. Here, psychology is very closely connected with didactics.

Nevertheless, in today's environment, when more and more of our citizens are interacting with native English speakers or fluent speakers of other languages, the importance of speaking practice is undeniable. There is no substitute for overcoming the so-called language or communication barrier, i.e. the psychological fear of speaking English. In modern pedagogical practice, foreign language teachers often face a situation where a person who has successfully learned a foreign language falls into a situation of social interaction in this language at home or in professional activities. At the same time, he copes well with being modeled by the teacher in the classroom. In real communication, the language barrier prevents him from realizing his linguistic knowledge, skills and abilities.

Educators and linguistic psychologists agree that language barriers often prevent adults from successfully acquiring a foreign language, and they can be internal or external.

External obstacles are objective and appear in front of a person regardless of his will. For example, he may not be able to choose a suitable teaching method that meets his goals or find a suitable teacher. Certain organizational actions are required to eliminate them. Internal obstacles are subjective, they are more difficult to overcome because they are created within us and their roots can be very deep in your subconscious.

RESULTS.

The psychology of language primarily deals with subjective, internal obstacles. The first and main obstacle to overcome when starting to learn a foreign language is overcoming the initial fear of this seemingly difficult task. As a rule, such obstacles appear in people who start learning a foreign language as adults. An adult should make his own decision.

This fear can be associated with, for example, the possibility of failure and loss of self-confidence. For many Russians, the main fear when speaking in a foreign language is still the fear of making grammatical mistakes. In this sense, it is still psychologically difficult for us to move away from the Soviet grammar-translation system, where formal correctness is the first priority, not the communicative value of the phrase. At the same time, we make grammatical mistakes quite calmly when speaking in our native language, sometimes we deliberately

break it for stylistic purposes, and this does not affect our communication in the language at all.

In the era of telecommunication technologies, it becomes clear that linguistic knowledge, which is nothing more than theoretical language information, is not enough for effective communication. Only having them and not having the ability to speak, we know the language in a "dead" form. This is the most common problem for people learning a foreign language using the traditional grammar-translation method.

To solve this problem, foreign language teaching in our country should have a communicative character and should be focused on real daily communication, which implies exchange of information not only through language, but also through emotions. In practice, this is very difficult to do, because such communication focuses on relaxation and enjoyment of the process itself. Our students and teachers in educational institutions are guided by standards and programs, which actually means focusing on a certain result, which is not always achieved.

In the process of learning a foreign language, didactic and pedagogical aspects are closely related to each other, because in this process we teach or learn speech, communication and master the system of its implementation. Communication training cannot be effective if it is considered within the framework of a "dry" methodology. Psychological aspects of language teaching determine not only the goals and objectives of teaching, motivation, student interest, etc., but also, apparently, specific learning styles and approaches, so the importance of language teaching is not neglected. can not be left. Psychological component in this educational process. Foreign language as an academic subject is very unique. It is not a science in itself, but all sciences and all areas of human knowledge are related to it, because there is no knowledge without language. That is why language learning has a great impact on the personal, general intellectual and general cultural development of a person, which once again emphasizes the important role of psychology in this process.

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